

Information sheet

Purpose of CHANGE

The Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and Environment (VKM) is leading the Collaboration to Harmonise the Assessment of Next Generation Evidence (CHANGE) project. The project is supported by the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (EBTC) and the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA). The project is funded by EFSA.

The aim of CHANGE is to contribute to regulatory acceptance and implementation of NAM data through identification of system-level interventions that could accelerate the utilisation of effective NAM methods in regulatory risk assessment and the risk management of chemical substances.

The project methodology involves documentation of personal experience of stakeholders in regulatory toxicology, the analysis of this experience for identifying system factors for intervention, and consensus-building around which interventions should be recommended for implementation.

Purpose of workshop 1

The goal of the first workshop in June 2024 in Oslo is to explore the structure and culture of regulatory toxicology to identify system-level factors that affect the acceptance, understanding, and utilization of NAM data from research through risk assessment to risk management.

There are no right or wrong responses during the workshop; we are seeking to hear your viewpoints and benefit from your experience.

The insights generated in the workshop will be analysed, made available publicly in reports, publications or presentations, and will serve to inform the future work in CHANGE.

Procedure and data collection during workshop 1

Workshop 1 will feature presentations to prime group discussion, and facilitated interactive sessions (including small group discussions, and larger “fishbowl” sessions). During these interactive sessions, you will share and discuss with other workshop participants your experiences of working around NAMs in the regulatory toxicology context.

During these interactive sessions, audio recordings will be made for the purpose of creating machine-generated transcripts. Participants will not be asked to introduce themselves at the beginning of the recording. Notes will be taken in the form of structured mind maps and

other written ways of recording discussion. This is the data from the workshop that will be analysed to develop the project findings.

During these interactive formats, you have the right to flag statements made by you as being off the record (so struck from the transcripts) by clearly stating that you wish for the piece of information to not be recorded in the transcripts (e.g., “The following needs to be off the record...” or “This information is confidential” or “Please strike from the record what I just said”).

If you realise after an interactive session that you would like to flag a statement you have made as off-record or confidential, you can do so by contacting Gisle Solstad (gisle.solstad@vkm.no) and specifying the session and statement.

You can flag your statements as confidential until one week after the workshop (deadline: June 27th, 2024, noon). After this deadline, we will initiate the pseudonymisation procedure and therefore not be able to identify and delete individual contributions.

Data management and processing after workshop 1

The VKM is a scientifically independent, administrative unit within the Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH), using the same servers and IT-security systems as the NIPH. All research data generated in the workshop, specifically the audio recording, machine generated transcripts, notes and mind maps, will be securely stored on a restricted area on VKM/NIPH's password-protected and access-controlled servers, and only available to specific VKM/NIPH employees from the project team.

The original audio recordings and transcripts will be deleted after the material is pseudonymised by the employees of VKM/NIPH, from the project group. Pseudonymisation will encompass the removing of directly identifiable information (i.e., person names, institutions and specific chemical substances).

While we will strive to protect everyone's privacy through this process, it might still be possible to reverse-engineer the institutional identity through contextual cues and indirectly identifiable information.

After the pseudonymising process, the data will be transferred from the restricted area on VKM/NIPH's password-protected and access-controlled servers to the VKM/NIPH password protected project area on Microsoft SharePoint. At this point, all Project Group members will have access to this data, for the purpose of analysis in relation to delivering the CHANGE objectives.

The project group will publish overall findings from the research and will do so in a way that does not allow individuals or the organisations that they work for to be identified. The pseudonymised transcripts will not be made publicly available but will be made available by request for research projects on a case-by-case basis (requiring a formal ethical approval and a data management plan from the interested party).

After the project, the data will be stored in VKM/NIPH's password protected data repository. This data will not be deleted.

Are there any risks or benefits associated with my participation in workshop 1?

No risks are expected, beyond those experienced during the participation in a workshop.

We will ask all workshop participants to observe the Chatham House Rules (<https://www.chathamhouse.org/about-us/chatham-house-rule>) to ensure an open, creative and trustful environment during the workshop. That means that participants are free to use the information received at the workshop, but they must not attribute any statements to any participant.

Right to withdraw

Participation in the workshop is voluntary and unpaid, except where participants are having their travel expenses reimbursed. We expect the discussions to be compelling and interesting.

The workshop does not involve the collection or processing of personal data and is therefore exempt from requiring a data protection impact assessment (DPIA) according to the Norwegian legislation. Since no biological materials or information on health will be collected and/or processed in the workshop, the workshop is also exempt from requiring ethics approval.

In planning the workshop, we have recognised participant concerns about risk to reputation of individuals or organisations from statements being attributable to individual participants. We have therefore implemented measures to promote confidentiality of contribution through pseudonymisation procedures, allowing participants to speak off the record, and to delete raw data after pseudonymisation is complete.

If you ever feel uncomfortable in any way during the workshop, you have the right to decline to answer any questions, participate in any group discussion or session, and to leave the workshop premises at any time without giving a reason.

What if I have a complaint or concerns?

If you have any complaints or concerns at all, please direct these to

- Gro Mathisen, VKM, Project Manager CHANGE - gro.haarklou.mathisen@vkm.no

and/or

- Kjersti Haugan, Norwegian Institute for Public Health, Data Protection Officer – kjersti.haugan@fhi.no

Contact

This project is led by Gro Mathisen. The research is planned and conducted by the project group.

If you have any queries, please contact:

- Gro Mathisen, VKM, Project Manager CHANGE – gro.haarklou.mathisen@vkm.no

Informed Consent Form

Please read the "Information Sheet" carefully and contact us if anything is unclear or you require more information.

I, the participant, confirm by my signature given below that:

- I have read and understood the information about CHANGE and workshop 1. My questions have been answered completely and to my satisfaction.
- I am aware of my rights and restrictions to be observed during and after participation in workshop 1.
- I have had enough time to decide about my participation.
- I participate in workshop 1 voluntarily and consent that my personal data be used as described above.
- I will respect the privacy of other workshop participants according to the rules mentioned above.

Time and place

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Signature participant

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Time and place

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Signature on-site contact person

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